

GENERAL ARTICLE

Zoopharmacognosy – Self medication behaviour in insects

Lalbiakzuali^{1*}, Lakshmikant M. K.² & Pushpa Singh³

¹Department of Entomology, Dr. Rajendra Prasad Central Agricultural University, Pusa, Samastipur – 848125, Bihar, India

²Department of Entomology, University of Agricultural Sciences, Raichur – 584104, Karnataka, India

³Department of Entomology, Dr. Rajendra Prasad Central Agricultural University, Pusa, Samastipur – 848125, Bihar, India

*lalbiakzualiralteralte@gmail.com

Abstract

Self-medication in insects, a fascinating aspect of zoopharmacognosy, demonstrates how these small yet complex organisms utilize environmental resources to combat pathogens and parasites. Despite their small size, they exhibit complex behaviours like consuming toxic plants or using anti-microbial resins to prevent or treat infections. Two primary forms of self-medication exist: *prophylactic* (preventive) and *therapeutic* (curative), which may benefit individuals or their kin. Examples include fruit flies ingesting ethanol to kill parasitoids, monarch butterflies choosing antiparasitic milkweed for eggs, and ants adding anti-microbial resins to nests. These behaviours meet self-medication criteria, such as deliberate substance use and fitness benefits. While insect immune defences (e.g., cuticles, melanization) is their first defence, self-medication acts as a secondary strategy. Research highlights its ecological and evolutionary importance, revealing intricate species interactions. Protecting these “tiny pharmacists” and their habitats is crucial for ecosystem health.

Keywords: defence, insects, parasites, self – medication, zoopharmacognosy

Introduction

Humans in the world are suffering with different kinds of diseases and even fatal sometimes. We came up with ways to protect ourselves from these diseases through drugs and vaccines. However, this ability isn't unique to humans; numerous animals, including elephants, chimpanzees, dogs, and even insects, exhibit self-medication behaviours by consuming or applying natural substances to prevent or treat illnesses. While evidence remains largely observational, such practices are widespread across the animal kingdom, often in unexpected ways. This phenomenon, termed zoopharmacognosy (from Greek: zoo = animal, pharmacon = drug, gnosy

= knowledge), refers to animals' innate ability to self-medicate (Ashwini & Patel, 2022). The concept was first introduced in 1978 by Daniel H. Janzen, an evolutionary ecologist at the University of Pennsylvania (Raman & Kandula, 2008). From mammals to insects, these behaviours highlight nature's remarkable adaptability, demonstrating how even the simplest organisms leverage their environment for survival and health management.

Criteria for self – medication

In order to consider the behaviour performed by an animals is a legitimate self-medication, there are four important criteria that must be followed. The first three were proposed by

Clayton and Wolfe (1993):

1. The substance in question must be deliberately contacted.
2. The substance must be detrimental to one or more parasites.
3. The detrimental effect on parasites must lead to increased host fitness.
4. The substance must have a detrimental effect on the host in the absence of parasites (Singer *et al.*, 2009)

Modes of self – medication

Self-medication can be classified into four categories according to the mode of contact: ingestion, absorption, topical application and proximity.

- a. Ingestion: Nicotine ingested by the tobacco hornworm (*Manduca sexta*) reduces colony growth and toxicity of *Bacillus thuringiensis*, leading to an increase in the survivorship of the hornworm (Krischik *et al.*, 1988).
- b. Absorption: Absorption of medicinal substances across skin or mucous membranes is another potential mode of self-medication. Chimpanzees massage *Aspilia* leaves with the

tongue for up to 25 seconds before swallowing the leaves which may facilitate absorption of Thiarubrine A, a potent antibiotic to treat their gastric acidic conditions (Clayton and Wolfe, 1993).

- c. Topical Application: A better known example is 'anting' behaviour of birds, during which bird grasps an ant in its bill and rubs it frenetically through its plumage. The fact that birds ant exclusively with ants that secrete acid or other pungent fluids suggests that anting may play some role in ectoparasite defence (Ehrlich *et al.*, 1986).
- d. Proximity: Gall-wasps developing galls benefit indirectly from tannin-rich oak leaves, showing reduced fungal attacks and higher survival rates. Tannin levels vary among oaks, influencing gall density and wasp diversity. This suggests wasps depend on host tannins for fungal defence, despite no direct contact with the compounds (Taper *et al.*, 1986).

Evidence of Zoopharmacognosy in Insects

An insect has two lines of defence system. First, its cuticle acts as a barrier to keep pathogens away, and second, their immune systems can combat infection if the pathogen penetrates this

layer which includes melanisation, encapsulation, and the production of antimicrobial peptides that comes into play (Fig 1). When neither of these defence systems is effective, an insect can look to its habitats for compounds that will aid to fight against infections then self-medication may be an alternative (Ashwini and Patel, 2022).

Insects do performed self – medication through various which includes:

- ✓ Change diet composition
- ✓ Ingest antiparasitic toxins
- ✓ Alter nutritional intake
- ✓ Change ovipositional sites
- ✓ Collection and storage of antimicrobial substances (Singer *et al.*, 2009).

Types of Insects Zoopharmacognosy

By using the four criteria listed above, we can distinguish true self-medication behaviour from other related phenomena such as prophylactic consumption or compensatory diet choice. The key factor in distinguishing self-medication from other actions is whether the substance involved is harmful to the consumer, as outlined in criterion 4. Dose-dependency plays a crucial role here as many compounds that are safe or even beneficial in small amounts can become toxic at higher doses. Another useful way to categorize these behaviours is based on timing: whether the substance is taken before or after infection. While not explicitly included in the original criteria, substances consumed to prevent infection (prophylaxis) may differ from those used to treat an active infection (therapeutic medication) (de Roode *et al.*, 2013). Combining these two factors creates a matrix of four related categories, all of which may affect parasite resistance or tolerance - but only two of these qualify as true

self-medication. (Fig 2).

a. Non-toxic substances that are consumed prophylactically

This category is quite broad, as it could encompass nearly any food that enhances general health or immune response. For instance, one study showed that alkaloids in nectar can lower pathogen levels in bumblebees (*Bombus terrestris*) without harming them (Manson *et al.*, 2010). When infected with the trypanosome parasite *Crithidia bombi*, bees that had previously consumed nest-mate faeces developed significantly milder infections compared to control groups.

b. Non-toxic substances that are consumed therapeutically

When infected individuals consume specific substances without apparent costs, this represents compensatory diet choice. For instance, infected individuals of the beetle (*Tenebrio molitor*) increased protein consumption relative to uninfected individuals, allowing them to offset costs of infection. Notably, higher protein consumption did not negatively affect the fitness of healthy beetles (Ponton *et al.*, 2011).

c. Prophylactic self-medication

Ants and bees exhibit prophylactic self-medication

by gathering antimicrobial or antifungal resins to shield their colonies from bacterial and fungal infections. However, the timing of resin collection varies between these insects. For example, wood ants (*Formica paralugubris*) practice social prophylaxis by harvesting antimicrobial resin from conifers, which helps prevent bacterial outbreaks within the colony (Castella *et al.*, 2008).

d. Therapeutic self-medication

The best example for this is seen in fruit flies. In their natural habitat, these flies encounter fermenting foods that produce alcohol. Uninfected flies avoid high-ethanol foods, as alcohol consumption reduces their fitness. However, when parasitoid wasps are present in them, consuming alcohol-producing food is a smart decision because it aids in the killing of wasp larvae. In this case, “drunk” flies actually outlive their “sober” counterparts. (Milan *et al.*, 2012) (Fig 3).

Targets of Zoopharmacognosy

Therapeutic and prophylactic medication

can be further divided depending on the target of medication: Self – medication and kin medication. “Self-medication” refers to when an insect actively seeks out substances that help them combat diseases or parasites in them. Example, Fruit Flies (*Drosophila melanogaster*) when infected with parasites, fruit flies seek out ethanol-rich (fermented) food, which helps reduce parasite loads. “Kin medication” refers to the application or ingestion of substances to prevent their offspring or their genetic kin, which may be prophylactically or therapeutically. Example, parasite-infected monarch butterflies (*Danaus plexippus*) can protect their offspring against high levels of parasite (*Oprhycystis elektroscirrha*) growth and virulence by laying their eggs on antiparasitic milkweed (transgenerational therapeutic medication) (Lefèvre *et al.*, 2012).

Self-Medication Behaviours & Metabolic Adaptations in Insects

Zoopharmacognosy in insects involves the deliberate consumption or use of bioactive

Figure. 3. Parasitized fruit fly used Ethanol for self – medication (Milan *et al.*, 2012)

substances to prevent or treat infections, parasitism, or toxins. These behaviours are often linked to specific metabolic adaptations that allow insects to process, detoxify, or sequester these compounds. Below are key examples and mechanisms:

- a. Detoxification & sequestration of plant toxins:** Monarch Butterflies (*Danaus plexippus*) feed and lay eggs on milkweed, which contains toxic cardenolides. They have evolved modified Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase enzymes that resist cardenolide binding, alongside cytochrome P450s (CYPs) to metabolize excess toxins. This adaptation allows them to sequester cardenolides for defence against predators or parasitoids (Petschenka *et al.*, 2018).
- b. Ethanol consumption to combat parasitoids:** Fruit Flies (*Drosophila melanogaster*) self-medicate by consuming ethanol when infected by parasitoid wasps. They metabolize ethanol using alcohol dehydrogenase (ADH), which intoxicates and kills the parasitoid larvae inside them (Milan *et al.*, 2012). This behaviour increases survival rates among parasitized flies.
- c. Antimicrobial use of plant resins and propolis:** Wood Ants (*Formica paralugubris*) collect antimicrobial tree resin and incorporate it into their nests. The resin's terpenoids inhibit fungal growth, and ants may metabolize these compounds via CYP450s (Chapuisat *et al.*, 2007). Honey Bees (*Apis mellifera*) use propolis to line hives. Their gut microbiota and detox enzymes (GSTs, UGTs) help process these compounds, providing protection against bacterial and fungal infections (Mao *et al.*, 2013).

Why should we study about insect self-medication?

- a. Evolutionary Insights into Medicinal Behaviour:**

Insects, like other animals, have evolved behaviours to combat pathogens and parasites. Studying self-medication in insects (e.g., parasitoid-infected flies consuming ethanol or monarch butterflies using anti-parasitic milkweed) helps us understand the origins of medication behaviours in animals (de Roode *et al.*, 2013).

- b. Potential for Novel Drug Discovery:** Scientists have looked at everything from traditional native remedies to marine microorganisms in their search for novel drugs. Despite the numerous differences between humans and insects, there have already been cases in which compounds present in human drugs have also been used by insects. Cardenolides used by the insects, have been utilized to treat both cancer and heart failure. Insects use bioactive plant compounds to self-medicate, which may inspire new antimicrobial or antiparasitic drugs for humans (e.g., honeybees using resinous propolis to inhibit fungal infections) (Simone-Finstrom and Spivak, 2012).
- c. Ecological and Conservation Implications:** Understanding self-medication helps assess how environmental changes (e.g., pesticide use or habitat loss) disrupt insect health by limiting access to medicinal plants (Singer *et al.*, 2009).
- d. Comparative Studies on Animal Cognition and Immunity:** Insect self-medication challenges assumptions about “simple” organisms and reveals complex host-parasite interactions (Abbott *et al.*, 2014).

Conclusion

Identifying deliberate self-medication in animals or insects can be challenging since many food plants also have medicinal qualities and the

boundaries between food and medicine can at times be hazy. In their natural habitats, animals select beneficial plants, possibly to treat health issues. Studying this behaviour can accelerate drug discovery, especially in ecosystems at risk. Just as human medicine learns from indigenous knowledge, animal self-medication offers valuable insights. To confirm self-medication, researchers must assess whether a behaviour reduces parasites and improves host fitness, then determine how the substance works. Insects, though small and seemingly simple, demonstrate remarkable medicinal behaviours that could inspire new human treatments. Their ability to self-medicate highlights nature's untapped potential for drug development. Future breakthroughs may even stem from compounds first used by insects, proving that these tiny creatures hold big promise for the discovery of new medicines.

References

- Abbott, J. (2014). Self-medication in insects: Current evidence and future perspectives. *Ecological Entomology*, 39(3), 273–280.
- Ashwini, M., & Patel, D. H. (2022). Insect zoopharmacognosy. *Agriculture and Food: E-Newsletter*, 4(4), 209–212.
- Castella, G., Chapuisat, M., & Christe, P. (2008). Prophylaxis with resin in wood ants. *Animal Behaviour*, 75(5), 1591–1596.
- Chapuisat, M., Oppliger, A., Magliano, P., & Christe, P. (2007). Wood ants use resin to protect themselves against pathogens. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 274(1621), 2013–2017.
- Clayton, D. H., & Wolfe, N. D. (1993). The adaptive significance of self-medication. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 8(2), 60–63.
- de Roode, J. C., Lefevre, T., & Hunter, M. D. (2013). Self-medication in animals. *Science*, 340(6129), 150–151.
- de Roode, J. C., & Hunter, M. D. (2019). Self-medication in insects: When altered behaviours of infected insects are a defense instead of a parasite manipulation. *Current Opinion in Insect Science*, 33, 1–6.
- Ehrlich, P. R., Dobkin, D. S., & Wheye, D. (1986). The adaptive significance of anting. *The Auk*, 103(4), 29–34.
- Krischik, V. A., Barbosa, P., & Reichelderfer, C. F. (1988). Three trophic level interactions: Allelochemicals, *Manduca sexta* (L.), and *Bacillus thuringiensis* var. *kurstaki* Berliner. *Environmental Entomology*, 17(3), 476–482.
- Lefèvre, T., Chiang, A., Kelavkar, M., Li, H., Li, J., de Castillejo, C. L. F., Oliver, L., Potini, Y., Hunter, M. D., & de Roode, J. C. (2012). Behavioural resistance against a protozoan parasite in the monarch butterfly. *Journal of Animal Ecology*, 81(1), 70–79.
- Manniello, M. D., Moretta, A., Salvia, R., Scieuzo, C., Lucchetti, D., Vogel, H., Sgambato, A., & Falabella, P. (2021). Insect antimicrobial peptides: Potential weapons to counteract the antibiotic resistance. *Cellular and Molecular Life Sciences*, 78(9), 4259–4282.
- Manson, J. S., Otterstatter, M. C., & Thomson, J. D. (2010). Consumption of a nectar alkaloid reduces pathogen load in bumble bees. *Oecologia*, 162(1), 81–89.
- Mao, W., Schuler, M. A., & Berenbaum, M. R. (2013). Honey constituents up-regulate

- detoxification and immunity genes in the western honey bee *Apis mellifera*. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 110(22), 8842–8846.
- Milan, N. F., Kacsoh, B. Z., & Schlenke, T. A. (2012). Alcohol consumption as self-medication against blood-borne parasites in the fruit fly. *Current Biology*, 22(6), 488–493.
- Petschenka, G., Fei, C. S., Araya, J. J., Schröder, S., Timmermann, B. N., & Agrawal, A. A. (2018). Relative selectivity of plant cardenolides for Na⁺/K⁺-ATPases from the monarch butterfly and non-resistant insects. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 9, 1424. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2018.01424>
- Ponton, F., Lalubin, F., Fromont, C., Wilson, K., Behm, C., & Simpson, S. J. (2011). Hosts use altered macronutrient intake to circumvent parasite-induced reduction in fecundity. *International Journal for Parasitology*, 41(1), 43–50.
- Raman, R., & Kandula, S. (2008). Zoopharmacognosy: Self-medication in wild animals. *Resonance*, 13(3), 245–253.
- Simone-Finstrom, M. D., & Spivak, M. (2012). Increased resin collection after parasite challenge: A case of self-medication in honey bees? *PLoS ONE*, 7(3), e34601. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0034601>
- Singer, M. S., Mace, K. C., & Bernays, E. A. (2009). Self-medication as adaptive plasticity: Increased ingestion of plant toxins by parasitized caterpillars. *PLoS ONE*, 4(3), e4796. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0004796>
- Taper, M. L., Zimmerman, E. M., & Case, T. J. (1986). Sources of mortality for a cynipid gall-wasp (*Dryocosmus dubiosus* [Hymenoptera: Cynipidae]): The importance of the tannin/fungus interaction. *Oecologia*, 68(3), 437–445.